

Supplementary Information for:

Ancient introgression in mouse lemurs (*Microcebus*:Cheirogaleidae) explains 20 years of phylogenetic uncertainty

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Supplementary Figures

Figure S1 – Change in log pseudolikelihood score in network estimates from SNaQ with respect to the maximum allowed number of reticulations.

Figure S2 – Node labels used to differentiate parameters for the MSci model analysis. Node h was unconstrained, such that it could have an older divergence time than the age of introgression node i . Node i will have two population size parameters, one from s into i and one from h into i .

Figure S3 – Convergence of divergence time parameters from the MSci analysis.
Individual violin plots correspond to four independent runs. The y-axes are in units of substitutions per site.

Figure S4 – Convergence of theta parameters from the MSci analysis. Individual violin plots correspond to four independent runs. Additional plots show the introgression probability estimates from node *s* to node *i*, the log-likelihoods, and a scatterplot of median node height estimates. The one-to-one correspondence of divergence times implied the MSci parameter estimates converged given our MCMC settings and model specification. The y-axes for theta parameters are the expected number of nucleotide differences per site between two sequences. The phi parameter is the introgression probability, which is bound between 0 and 1.

Figure S5 – *Microcebus* phylogenetic network using SVDQuartets topology as starting tree. Node support values in black represent bootstrap support percentages from 100 bootstrap replicates. These node support values correspond to hybrid edge and hybrid node support in addition to bifurcating node support. The minor hybrid edge is colored blue while the major hybrid edge is colored purple. The inheritance probability (γ) for the minor hybrid edge is depicted in blue with one standard deviation.

Figure S6 — Bootstrap support of each individual for select *Microcebus* relationships. Each point corresponds to the bootstrap support of an individual gene tree that supports a given relationship.

Figure S7 – Signatures of introgression among species of *Microcebus* from untrimmed dataset. Gene tree frequency tests were performed using (A) the maximum likelihood species tree topology and (B) the major phylogenetic network topology. Left: D (above diagonal) and f_4 -ratio (below diagonal) statistics depicting estimated gene flow between species pairs. Right: f_b -branch statistic with compatible tests shown in grey.

Supplementary Tables

Table S1 – Published genomes used for analyses.

species	Genome ID	Biosample ID	Reference
<i>Mirza zaza</i>	GCA_008750895.1	SAMN10707785	Hunnicut et al. 2020
<i>Microcebus griseorufus</i>	GCA_008750995.1	SAMN10707780	Hunnicut et al. 2020
<i>Microcebus murinus</i>	GCA_000165445.3	SAMN06275470	Larsen et al. 2017
<i>Microcebus ravelobensis</i>	GCA_008750975.1	SAMN10707782	Hunnicut et al. 2020
<i>Microcebus jonahi</i>	GCA_008750915.1	SAMN10707783	Poelstra et al. 2021
<i>Microcebus tavaratra</i>	GCA_008750935.1	SAMN10707784	Hunnicut et al. 2020
<i>Microcebus mittermieri</i>	GCA_008750955.1	SAMN10707781	Hunnicut et al. 2020

Table S2 – Missing data statistics among species.

species	# sequences	% missing	gene length[†]	% missing[†]	total sites	% missing sites
<i>Mirza zaza</i>	3942	4.94	1567 ± 20	4.08 ± 0.3	6177882	0.0822
<i>Microcebus griseorufus</i>	3954	4.65	1476 ± 19	7.94 ± 0.4	5838723	0.133
<i>Microcebus murinus</i>	3943	4.9	1514 ± 21	1.64 ± 0.1	6280402	6.7
<i>Microcebus ravelobensis</i>	3938	5.04	1473 ± 19	8.7 ± 0.4	5801314	0.138
<i>Microcebus jonahi</i>	3979	4.05	1556 ± 20	4.34 ± 0.3	6192206	0.08
<i>Microcebus tavaratra</i>	4018	3.11	1536 ± 20	5.04 ± 0.3	6171939	0.0831
<i>Microcebus mittermieri</i>	4005	3.42	1430 ± 19	7.54 ± 0.4	5930538	0.119
Alignments	4147	NA	1623 ± 20	NA	6731343	NA

[†]The gene length is based on alignments where the species was present. The mean and symmetric normal approximation of the 95% confidence interval are given.

Table S3 – Introgression test statistics from the untrimmed dataset. The *D* and *f4*-ratio statistics are reported for each rooted trio that is consistent with the maximum likelihood (ML), major network (network), or both (Both) tree topologies. A significant test indicates significant signature of introgression between P2 and P3. Significance codes: n.s., not significant; *, adjusted *P* < 0.05; **, adjusted *P* < 0.01; ***, adjusted *P* < 0.001.

Topology	P1	P2	P3	<i>D</i>	<i>f4</i> -ratio	Significance
Both	<i>M. jonahi</i>	<i>M. mittermeieri</i>	<i>M. griseorufus</i>	0.11	0.02	**
Both	<i>M. murinus</i>	<i>M. griseorufus</i>	<i>M. jonahi</i>	0.18	0.03	***
ML	<i>M. griseorufus</i>	<i>M. ravelobensis</i>	<i>M. johani</i>	0.11	0.03	**
Network	<i>M. johani</i>	<i>M. ravelobensis</i>	<i>M. griseorufus</i>	0.33	0.11	***
Both	<i>M. johani</i>	<i>M. tavaratra</i>	<i>M. griseorufus</i>	0.04	0.01	n.s.
Both	<i>M. murinus</i>	<i>M. griseorufus</i>	<i>M. mittermeieri</i>	0.24	0.04	***
ML	<i>M. griseorufus</i>	<i>M. ravelobensis</i>	<i>M. mittermeieri</i>	0.12	0.04	***
Network	<i>M. mittermeieri</i>	<i>M. ravelobensis</i>	<i>M. griseorufus</i>	0.26	0.09	***
Both	<i>M. tavaratra</i>	<i>M. mittermeieri</i>	<i>M. griseorufus</i>	0.09	0.02	*
Both	<i>M. murinus</i>	<i>M. griseorufus</i>	<i>M. ravelobensis</i>	0.20	0.03	***
Both	<i>M. murinus</i>	<i>M. griseorufus</i>	<i>M. tavaratra</i>	0.19	0.03	***
ML	<i>M. griseorufus</i>	<i>M. ravelobensis</i>	<i>M. tavaratra</i>	0.12	0.03	**
Network	<i>M. tavaratra</i>	<i>M. ravelobensis</i>	<i>M. griseorufus</i>	0.30	0.10	***
Both	<i>M. jonahi</i>	<i>M. mittermeieri</i>	<i>M. murinus</i>	0.08	0.01	**
Both	<i>M. jonahi</i>	<i>M. mittermeieri</i>	<i>M. ravelobensis</i>	0.12	0.03	***
Both	<i>M. tavaratra</i>	<i>M. mittermeieri</i>	<i>M. jonahi</i>	0.11	0.02	**
ML	<i>M. murinus</i>	<i>M. ravelobensis</i>	<i>M. jonahi</i>	0.22	0.06	***
Network	<i>M. jonahi</i>	<i>M. ravelobensis</i>	<i>M. murinus</i>	0.34	0.08	***
Both	<i>M. jonahi</i>	<i>M. tavaratra</i>	<i>M. murinus</i>	0.04	0.01	n.s.
Both	<i>M. jonahi</i>	<i>M. tavaratra</i>	<i>M. ravelobensis</i>	0.05	0.01	n.s.
ML	<i>M. murinus</i>	<i>M. ravelobensis</i>	<i>M. mittermeieri</i>	0.25	0.08	***
Network	<i>M. mittermeieri</i>	<i>M. ravelobensis</i>	<i>M. murinus</i>	0.30	0.07	***
Both	<i>M. tavaratra</i>	<i>M. mittermeieri</i>	<i>M. murinus</i>	0.05	0.01	n.s.
Both	<i>M. tavaratra</i>	<i>M. mittermeieri</i>	<i>M. ravelobensis</i>	0.08	0.01	n.s.
ML	<i>M. murinus</i>	<i>M. ravelobensis</i>	<i>M. tavaratra</i>	0.23	0.06	***
Network	<i>M. tavaratra</i>	<i>M. ravelobensis</i>	<i>M. murinus</i>	0.32	0.08	***